

**Vaginal V/S Intramuscular Use of Progesterone and its Efficacy in preventing the preterm labor:
A comparative Study.**

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Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of this study was to find the efficacy of use of progesterone either vaginally or intramuscularly in avoiding the preterm labor.

Place of Study: This study was carried out in Gynecology and Obstetrics department of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore.

Duration of study: This study was carried out in a duration of 9 months from February 2018 to October 2018.

Materials and Methods: A total of 200 patients were selected and divided into two groups having 100 patients in each group. The patients were between the ages of 25 to 35 years with parity five. In all the patients history of preterm delivery was present and they were at 20 to 24th week of gestation. Vaginal administration of 200mg progesterone was done (pessary) once a day in group A while weekly administration of 250mg was given intramuscularly. It was continued till 37th completed weeks. The follow up of the patients was strictly observed and maintained via telephonic contact.

Results: Progesterone administered vaginally had higher efficacy of 71% in preventing the preterm labor as compared to intramuscular route in which efficacy of 52% was noted.

Conclusion: Progesterone given to the patient via vaginal route has greater efficacy in preventing the preterm labor as compared to the ones in which Intramuscular route was used for progesterone administration.

Keywords: progesterone, intramuscular, vaginal, efficacy.

Introduction: Delivery occurring before 37 weeks of gestation is defined as preterm birth. Preterm delivery leads to increased rate of mortality and morbidity. CNS defects are also seen in the late stages of life due to pre mature birth. Incidence of preterm deliveries is increasing and almost 15% incidence have been reported even in developed countries.

Clinical symptoms like uterine contractions, dilation of the cervix and effacement are used for diagnosing premature labor. Presence of vaginal

bleeding or evidence of ruptured membrane gives the definite diagnosis of preterm labor. It is due to poorly prediction of diagnosis until the labor is well established whereas over-diagnosis is reported commonly.

For the first time in 1934, progesterone was identified but its role in supporting the myometrium was 1st identified in 1954. In past multiple studies have been done to identify the role of 17-alpha-hydroxy-progesterone administered intramuscularly or vaginally to avoid the preterm labor.

But in many recent studies there is a controversy in use of progesterone intramuscularly or vaginally to prevent the preterm labor.

Aim of our study is to find the authenticity of use of progesterone to prevent the preterm labor which will be helpful and beneficial in our society for patients and obstetricians as well.

Materials and Methods: A total of 200 patients were selected and divided into two groups having 100 patients in each group. The patients were between the ages of 25 to 35 years with parity five. In all the patients history of preterm delivery was present and they were at 20 to 24th week of gestation. Vaginal administration of 200mg progesterone was done (pessary) once a day in group A while weekly administration of 250mg was given intramuscularly. It was continued till 37th completed weeks. The follow up of the patients was strictly observed and maintained via telephonic contact.

Results: Progesterone administered vaginally had higher efficacy of 71% in preventing the preterm labor as compared to intramuscular route in which efficacy of 52% was noted.

Discussion: The studies conducted in past showed a controversy in efficacy of use of progesterone either via intramuscular route of vaginal route to prevent the preterm labor. But locally in our population very little work has been done to find

the efficacy of progesterone in preventing the preterm labor.

In our study progesterone administered vaginally had higher efficacy of 71% in preventing the preterm labor as compared to intramuscular route in which efficacy of 52% was noted.

Our study is in accordance with the recent study done by G. Saccone showing efficiency of progesterone used either vaginally or intramuscularly in preterm labor. They concluded on their study that at 16th week of gestation vaginal progesterone (pessary) is an effective and safe method to prevent the preterm labor.

In another research, it has been shown that natural progesterone i.e. vaginal progesterone is more safe and efficient as compared to intramuscular because of less side effects such as fatigue, sleepiness and headaches.

Equal efficacy of both intramuscular progesterone and vaginal pessary in preventing the preterm labor has been shown by Azza A. Abd El Hameed and colleagues in their study.

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Less significant births were seen with the use of vaginal progesterone as compared to intramuscular showing 16.6% with vaginal pessary and 25.7% with intramuscular progesterone.

Efficiency of progesterone given vaginally in preventing the preterm labor was assessed by Romero R and colleagues showed that it reduces the rate of preterm deliveries up to 30-35 weeks of gestation.

The reliability of vaginal progesterone is also supported by the fact that a large number of patients use these in the 2nd trimester for luteal support and in 2nd and 3rd trimester high risk group using progesterone supports efficacy in later stages.

However numerous trials reported insignificant increase in risk of stillbirth and miscarriage in pregnancies receiving progestins.

Conclusion: Progesterone given to the patient via vaginal route has greater efficacy in preventing the preterm labor as compared to the ones in which Intramuscular route was used for progesterone administration.

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